

Some New 2-Aryl-3-isonicotamido-4-thiazolidinones and their 5-Carboxymethyl Homologues as Potential Antitubercular and Antibacterial Agent

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4-Thiazolidinones of the type (II) have been synthesised by condensing hydrazones of the type (I) with thioglycolic acid in benzene solution. Hydrazones have been prepared by condensing different aromatic aldehydes with isoniazide in ethanol (95%). Compounds (I) and (II) showed remarkable antibacterial and antitubercular activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, strain H₁, R_v.

4-Thiazolidinones are well known for their wide spectra of pharmacological activities. Compounds with -N-C-S- structure are also reported to possess amoebicidal, anticonvulsant, anaesthetic, hypnotic, antitubercular, antifungal, anthelmentic, cardiovascular and antibacterial activity²⁻¹⁴.

The incorporation of isoniazide in the structure is based on the well established activity of the compound against various strains of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, with the expectation that the resultant compounds may possibly show higher LD₅₀.

The structure of the thiazolidinones have been elucidated on the basis of ir and uv spectra. The uv spectra of the 4-thiazolidinones with different substituents show similarities in having absorption around 295 nm. The ir spectra show the characteristic absorption bands at 1660, 1220, 2850, 1362, 3430, 1520 cm⁻¹. The peculiar band at 1220-1025 (s) cm⁻¹, which is found common in these com-

pounds, may be the absorption band for the thiazolidinone ring system.

Experimental

Preparation of 4-hydrazones (I) : Isoniazide (0.01 mole) was dissolved in ethanol (95%, 50 ml) and aryl aldehyde (0.01 mole) was added. The contents were refluxed for 3 hr and ethanol distilled off until the Schiff base commenced to crystallise out. The data are recorded in Table 1.

Preparation of 4-thiazolidinones (II)¹ :

(a) To hydrazones (I) (0.01 mole) in benzene (25 ml) was added thioglycolic acid. The contents were refluxed for 8 hr until water collected in Dean and Stark trap. Excess of benzene was removed under reduced pressure and the residue treated with saturated solution of NaHCO₃, extracted with ether, dried with Na₂SO₄ and ether distilled off. The residue on crystallisation gave 4-thiazolidinone.

TABLE I—HYDRAZONES OF THE TYPE (I)

Sl. No.	R	M. F.	m.p. °C	Antibacterial activity of hydrazones		
				<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Mycobacterium</i> (H ₁ , R _v)
1.	-3.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClNO ₂	212	+	-	+
2.	-4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ O	160	+	-	+
3.	-2.COOH.CH ₂ .O-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂	210	++	+	+
4.	-4-COOH.CH ₂ .O.3-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	252	++	+	+
5.	-5.NO ₂ .3.OCH ₃ -4.OH.C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂	238	++	+	+
6.	-3,4.CH ₃ .O ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	225	-	-	+
7.	-5.Br.2.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Br	258	++	+	+
8.	-3,4-di-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂	215	+	+	+
9.	-4.N(OH) ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ O	198	-	-	+
10.	-2.C ₆ H ₄ .OH ₂ .O.3,5-di.Br.C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	200	++	+	+

(+) Indicates inhibition zone diameter less than 20 mm ; (++) indicates inhibition zone diameter more than 200 mm ; The tuberculostatic concentration is 0.02 µg/ml. All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analysis.

TABLE 2—4-THIAZOLIDINONES OF THE TYPE (II)

Sl. No.	R	R'	M. F.	m.p. °C	Antibacterial activity of 4-thiazolidinones		
					<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Mycobacterium</i> (H ₃₇ R _v)
1.	-3.ClO ₂ H ₄	-H	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ClNO ₂ S	204	+	-	+
2.	-4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	-H	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	248	++	+	+
3.	-2.COOH.CH ₂ .O.C ₆ H ₄	-H	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	192	++	+	+
4.	-4.COOH.CH ₂ .O. 3.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	-H	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	178	++	+	+
5.	-5.NO ₂ .3.OCH ₃ . -4.OH.C ₆ H ₄	-H	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	167	++	+	+
6.	3,4-OH ₂ .O ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	-H	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	144	+	-	+
7.	-5.Br.2.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	-H	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	211	++	+	+
8.	-3,4-di.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	-H	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	149	+	+	+
9.	-3.ClO ₂ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ ClNO ₂ S	189	+	+	+
10.	-4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	238	+	-	+
11.	-2.COOH.CH ₂ .O.C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	185	+	+	+
12.	-4.COOH.CH ₂ .O. -3.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	202	++	+	+
13.	-5.NO ₂ .3.OCH ₃ . -4.OH.C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	157	+	-	+
14.	-3,4.OH ₂ .O ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	121	-	-	+
15.	-5.Br.2.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	179	+	+	+
16.	-3,4-di.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	168	+	-	+
17.	-4.N.(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	193	-	-	+
18.	-2.C ₆ H ₅ .CH ₂ .O. 3,5-di-Br.C ₆ H ₄	-CH ₂ .COOH	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	179	++	+	+

(+) Indicates inhibition zone diameter less than 20 mm ; (++) indicates inhibition zone diameter more than 20 mm ; The tubercular concentration is 0.02 µg/ml.

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analysis.

(b) Hydrazones (I) (0.01 mole) and thiomallic acid (0.01 mole) were condensed in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 hr. The temperature was raised to 180° and kept for 30 min. The product so obtained was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate (4 N) solution, filtered and reprecipitated from the filtrate with dil. hydrochloric acid and crystallised in ethanol.

Pharmacological screening :

The hydrazones and 4-thiazolidinones were screened for antituberculostatic and antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

Antitubercular activity : *In vitro* antitubercular activity of the synthesised hydrazones and 4-thiazolidinones were studied against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in Lowenstein-Jensen egg media at 0.02 mg/ml. The retardation of growth was studied upto 6 weeks at 37°.

Antibacterial activity : The antibacterial activities were tested by nutrient agar pour plate method and DMF solutions of the compounds were found active against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* in various concentration.

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